

ISic0685

I.Sicily inscription 0685

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari, Area archeologica Teatro antico e Antiquarium di Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493937

EDCS 32701127

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 164 no.16a fig.16

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385162>